

**MEAN VALUES OF THE PRODUCT OF AN INTEGER AND ITS
MODULAR INVERSE**

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Abstract

In this note, we extend a recent result of Chan (2016), that deals with mean values of the product of an integer and its multiplicative inverse modulo a prime number, to such products modulo a composite number.

1. Introduction

Let $k \geq 2$ be any integer. Chan [3] studies the sum $S_k(p) := \sum_{\substack{a_1=1 \\ a_1 \cdots a_k \equiv 1 \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \cdots \sum_{\substack{a_k=1 \\ a_k \equiv 1 \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} a_1 \cdots a_k$,

where p is a prime number, and shows that

$$S_k(p) = 2^{-k} p^k (p-1)^{k-1} + O(p^{\vartheta_k} (\log p)^k) \quad (1)$$

where $\vartheta_2 = \frac{5}{2}$ and $\vartheta_k = \frac{3k}{2}$ if $k \geq 3$. As can be seen in [3, Theorem 3], this result also holds for the more general sum

$$S_k(p, m) := \sum_{\substack{a_1=1 \\ a_1 \cdots a_k \equiv m \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \cdots \sum_{\substack{a_k=1 \\ a_k \equiv 1 \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} a_1 \cdots a_k$$

where m is any positive integer satisfying $(m, p) = 1$. The main aim of this work is to generalize the estimate (1) to any composite modulus $n \geq 2$. We therefore investigate the sum

$$S_k(n, m) := \sum_{\substack{a_1=1 \\ a_1 \cdots a_k \equiv m \pmod{n}}}^n \cdots \sum_{\substack{a_k=1 \\ a_k \equiv 1 \pmod{n}}}^n a_1 \cdots a_k, \quad (2)$$

where m is any positive integer satisfying $(m, n) = 1$, and with the convention that the sum $S_k(n, m)$ vanishes whenever there exists $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ such that $(a_j, n) > 1$. We will use the notation $f(n) = M(n) + O^*(R(n))$, meaning $|f(n) - M(n)| \leq R(n)$ for all integers $n \geq 2$.

Theorem 1. For $k \geq 3$, $n \geq 2$, and $m \geq 1$ such that $(m, n) = 1$,

$$S_k(n, m) = 2^{-k} n^k \varphi(n)^{k-1} + O^* \left((2\sqrt{3})^k n^{3k/2} (\log n)^k \right).$$

When $k \geq 4$ and $n \geq 3$ is odd, more recent results for mean values of odd Dirichlet characters enable us to slightly improve the above estimate.

Theorem 2. For $k \geq 4$, $n \geq 3$ odd, and $m \geq 1$ such that $(m, n) = 1$,

$$S_k(n, m) = 2^{-k} n^k \varphi(n)^{k-1} + O_k \left(n^{\frac{3}{2}(k-2)} \varphi(n)^3 (\log n)^{k-4} (\log \log n)^2 \right).$$

The implied constant in the error term depends on k .

The case $k = 2$ needs specific estimates involving additive characters and exponential sums. On the other hand, as in Theorem 1, we are able to give a fully explicit error term in this case.

Theorem 3. For all $n \geq 2$ and $m \geq 1$ such that $(m, n) = 1$,

$$S_2(n, m) = 4^{-1} n^2 \varphi(n) + O^* \left(n^2 \sigma_{1/2}(n) (\tau(n) \log en)^2 + \frac{1}{4} n \varphi(n) \right)$$

where $\sigma_{1/2}(n) := \sum_{d|n} \sqrt{d}$ and $\tau(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$.

To study the sharpness of the previous result, it can be helpful to investigate the mean square of its error term. When n is odd, we can prove the next result.

Theorem 4. For all $n \geq 3$ odd and all $\varepsilon > 0$ small, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,n)=1}}^n |S_2(n, m) - 4^{-1} n^2 \varphi(n)|^2 = \frac{5C_n}{144} (n\varphi(n))^3 + O(n^{5+\varepsilon})$$

where the constant C_n is given in Equation (4) below. In particular, for all sufficiently large odd integers n , there exists $m \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $(m, n) = 1$ and

$$|S_2(n, m) - 4^{-1} n^2 \varphi(n)| \gg n^{3/2} \varphi(n).$$

Note that $n^{3/2} \varphi(n) \gg n^{5/2} (\log \log n)^{-1}$ while $n^2 \sigma_{1/2}(n) (\tau(n) \log en)^2 \ll n^{5/2+\varepsilon}$. Hence, when n is odd, the error term in Theorem 3 is sharp apart from the n^ε -factor.

2. Notation

In what follows, $n \geq 2$, $k \geq 2$, and $m \geq 1$ are integers, and we always assume that $(m, n) = 1$. For all $x \in \mathbb{R}$, we set $e_n(x) := e^{\frac{2\pi i x}{n}}$, and $\|x\|$ is the distance to the nearest integer. As for arithmetic functions, μ is the Möbius function, φ is the Euler totient function and, for all $h \in \mathbb{R}$, let $\sigma_h(n) := \sum_{d|n} d^h$. It is customary to set $\tau := \sigma_0$. The main sum $S_k(n, m)$ studied here is defined in Equation (2).

3. Proofs of Theorems 1 and 2

Proof of Theorem 1. By the orthogonality relations of the Dirichlet characters, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} S_k(n, m) &= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{a_1=1}^n \cdots \sum_{a_k=1}^n a_1 \cdots a_k \sum_{\chi \pmod{n}} \bar{\chi}(m) \chi(a_1) \cdots \chi(a_k) \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\chi \pmod{n}} \bar{\chi}(m) \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a \chi(a) \right)^k \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \left(\sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a \right)^k + \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} \bar{\chi}(m) \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a \chi(a) \right)^k \\ &= 2^{-k} n^k \varphi(n)^{k-1} + R_k(n, m) \end{aligned}$$

with

$$R_k(n, m) := \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} \bar{\chi}(m) \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a \chi(a) \right)^k,$$

and using Abel summation [2, Corollary 1.1] and the Pólya-Vinogradov inequality [2, Theorem 6.10], we get

$$\left| \sum_{a \leq n} a \chi(a) \right| \leq 2n \max_{A \leq n} \left| \sum_{a \leq A} \chi(a) \right| \leq 2\sqrt{3} n^{3/2} \log n \tag{3}$$

so that $|R_k(n, m)| \leq (2\sqrt{3})^k n^{3k/2} (\log n)^k$. □

For the proof of Theorem 2, we assume $k \geq 4$ and suppose that $n \geq 3$ is an odd integer. The proof rests on the following result, which is [4, Lemma 9].

Lemma 1. *Let $q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 3}$ be odd and set*

$$C_q := \prod_{p^\alpha \parallel q} \left(1 + \frac{2p^3 + p^2 - 1}{(p^2 + 1)(p^2 + p + 1)} - \frac{1}{p^{3(\alpha-1)}(p^2 + p + 1)} \right). \tag{4}$$

Then, for all $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{q} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \bar{\chi}(2^\ell) \left| \sum_{a=1}^q a\chi(a) \right|^4 = C_q \frac{(3\ell + 5)q^3\varphi(q)^4}{72 \times 2^{\ell+1}} + O_\ell(q^{6+\varepsilon}).$$

We will make use of this result in the following weaker form.

Corollary 1. *Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 3}$ be odd. Then*

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4 \ll n^3\varphi(n)^4(\log \log n)^2. \tag{5}$$

Proof. Using Lemma 1 with $q = n$ odd and $\ell = 0$, we derive

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{q} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4 = C_n \frac{5n^3\varphi(n)^4}{144} + O(n^{6+\varepsilon})$$

where C_n is defined in Equation (4) above. Now

$$\prod_{p|n} \left(1 + \frac{4}{5p}\right) \leq C_n \leq \prod_{p|n} \left(1 + \frac{2}{p}\right),$$

so that C_n is unbounded and, using [2, Exercise 61], we get

$$C_n \leq \exp\left(2 \sum_{p|n} \frac{1}{p}\right) \leq \exp(2 \log \log \log n + 6) \leq (e^3 \log \log n)^2,$$

completing the proof. □

Remark 1. Note that bounding the inner sum of the left-hand side of the estimate (5) using the bound (3) would only give

$$\sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4 \ll n^6\varphi(n)(\log n)^4.$$

Proof of Theorem 2. First notice that, for all $\chi \neq \chi_0$, we have the identity $\sum_{a=1}^q a\chi(a) = -\chi(-1) \sum_{a=1}^q a\chi(a)$ (cf. the proof of [1, Theorem 12.20] which does not require q to be odd), so that, for all even Dirichlet characters $\chi \neq \chi_0$, we have

$$\sum_{a=1}^q a\chi(a) = 0. \tag{6}$$

Hence $S_k(n, m) = 2^{-k}n^k\varphi(n)^{k-1} + R_k^{\text{odd}}(n, m)$, where

$$R_k^{\text{odd}}(n, m) := \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \bar{\chi}(m) \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right)^k.$$

Now using (3) and Corollary 1, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^k &= \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^{k-4} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4 \\ &\ll n^{\frac{3}{2}(k-4)} (\log n)^{k-4} \times n^3 \varphi(n)^4 (\log \log n)^2 \\ &\ll n^{\frac{3}{2}(k-2)} \varphi(n)^4 (\log n)^{k-4} (\log \log n)^2 \end{aligned}$$

implying the asserted estimate. □

4. Proof of Theorem 3

4.1. Technical Lemmas

Lemma 2. For all $n, k, m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ such that $(m, n) = 1$,

$$\left| \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \right| \leq 2n^{3/2} \tau(n) (n, k)^{1/2} \log(en).$$

Proof. From Weil’s bound applied to Kloosterman sums and a completion device, it is known [2, (6.21) p. 454] that, for all positive integers $t \leq n$, we have

$$\left| \sum_{\substack{a \leq t \\ (a,n)=1}} e_n(km\bar{a}) \right| \leq n^{1/2} \tau(n) (n, mk)^{1/2} \log(en)$$

so that, by Abel summation, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \right| &\leq 2n \max_{t \leq n} \left| \sum_{\substack{a \leq t \\ (a,n)=1}} e_n(km\bar{a}) \right| \\ &\leq 2n^{3/2} \tau(n) (n, mk)^{1/2} \log(en) \end{aligned}$$

and we conclude the proof, noticing that $(n, mk) = (n, k)$ since $(n, m) = 1$. □

The next lemma is well-known, but we provide here a proof for the sake of completeness.

Lemma 3. *Let $q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 2}$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. If $q \nmid k$, then*

$$\sum_{b=1}^{q-1} b e_q(-kb) = \frac{-q}{1 - e_q(-k)}.$$

Proof. If $z^q = 1, z \neq 1$, then $\sum_{b=0}^{q-1} z^b = (1 - z^q)/(1 - z) = 0$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{b=1}^{q-1} b z^{b-1}\right) (1 - z) &= z + 2z^2 + \dots + (q - 1)z^{q-1} - z^2 - 2z^3 - \dots - (q - 1)z^q \\ &= z + z^2 + \dots + z^{q-1} - (q - 1)z^q = -1 - (q - 1) = -q. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 4. *For all $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 2}$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$,*

$$\sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ (b,n)=1}}^n b e_n(-kb) = -n \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}} \frac{\mu(d)}{1 - e_{n/d}(-k)} + \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d < n \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1\right).$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ (b,n)=1}}^n b e_n(-kb) &= \sum_{d|n} d\mu(d) \sum_{b \leq n/d} b e_n(-kdb) = \sum_{d|n} d\mu(d) \sum_{b \leq n/d} b e_{n/d}(-kb) \\ &= \sum_{d|n} d\mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} + \sum_{b \leq \frac{n}{d}-1} b e_{n/d}(-kb)\right) \\ &= n \underbrace{\sum_{d|n} \mu(d)}_{=0, \text{ since } n \geq 2} + \left(\sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}} + \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}}\right) d\mu(d) \sum_{b \leq \frac{n}{d}-1} b e_{n/d}(-kb) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}} d\mu(d) \frac{-n/d}{1 - e_{n/d}(-k)} + \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}} d\mu(d) \sum_{b \leq \frac{n}{d}-1} b \\ &= -n \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}} \frac{\mu(d)}{1 - e_{n/d}(-k)} + \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d < n \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1\right) \end{aligned}$$

where we used Vinogradov’s lemma [2, Corollary 4.6] in the 1st equality of the 1st line, and Lemma 3 in the 1st sum of the penultimate line. □

We will make use of the following principle.

Lemma 5. *Let $f : \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be any arithmetic function. Then, for any $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$,*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n f(k) = \sum_{d|n} \sum_{\substack{h=1 \\ (\frac{n}{d}, h)=1}}^{n/d} f(hd).$$

Proof. Set $d = (n, k)$ and sum over all values of $d \mid n$, assuming by convention that the inner sum vanishes if $d \nmid k$, yielding

$$\sum_{k=1}^n f(k) = \sum_{d|n} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ d|k \\ (\frac{n}{d}, \frac{k}{d})=1}}^n f(k).$$

The change $k = hd$ then gives the asserted result. □

Lemma 6. *Let $q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 2}$ and $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Then*

$$\sum_{\substack{a \pmod{q} \\ q \nmid a\ell}} \frac{1}{|1 - e_q(\pm a\ell)|} \leq \frac{q}{2} \log \left(\frac{eq}{2(\ell, q)} \right) < \frac{q}{2} \log(eq).$$

Proof. The inequality $|e(x) - e(y)| \geq 4\|x - y\|$ [2, Exercise 114] and periodicity yield

$$\sum_{\substack{a \pmod{q} \\ q \nmid a\ell}} \frac{1}{|1 - e_q(\pm a\ell)|} \leq \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ q \nmid a\ell}}^{q-1} \frac{1}{\|a\ell/q\|} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{j=1}^{q-1} \frac{1}{\|j/q\|} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a\ell \equiv j \pmod{q}}}^{q-1} 1.$$

For fixed ℓ, j , and q , the linear congruence $a\ell \equiv j \pmod{q}$ has solutions in a if and only if $(\ell, q) \mid j$, and in this case there are (ℓ, q) solutions \pmod{q} . Hence, with the notation $q/(\ell, q) := r$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{a \pmod{q} \\ q \nmid a\ell}} \frac{1}{|1 - e_q(\pm a\ell)|} &\leq \frac{(\ell, q)}{4} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (\ell, q) \mid j}}^{q-1} \frac{1}{\|j/q\|} = \frac{(\ell, q)}{4} \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} \frac{1}{\|t/r\|} \\ &= \frac{(\ell, q)}{4} \left(\sum_{t \leq r/2} \frac{r}{t} + \sum_{r/2 < t \leq r-1} \frac{r}{r-t} \right) \\ &\leq \frac{r(\ell, q)}{2} \sum_{t \leq r/2} \frac{1}{t} \leq \frac{q}{2} \log(er/2) < \frac{q}{2} \log(eq), \end{aligned}$$

as required. □

Lemma 7. *Let $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 2}$, and d be a divisor of n . Then*

$$\sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{(n, k)^{1/2}}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-k)|} \leq \frac{1}{2} n^{1/2} \sigma_{1/2}(n) \log(en).$$

Proof. Using Lemma 5 we first derive

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{(n, k)^{1/2}}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-k)|} &= \sum_{\substack{\delta|n \\ \delta < n}} \delta^{1/2} \sum_{\substack{h=1 \\ (\frac{n}{\delta}, h)=1 \\ \frac{n}{\delta} \nmid h\delta}}^{\frac{n}{\delta}-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-h\delta)|} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\delta|n \\ \delta < n}} \delta^{1/2} \sum_{\substack{h=1 \\ (\frac{n}{\delta}, h)=1 \\ \frac{n}{\delta} \nmid hd}}^{\frac{n}{\delta}-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e_{n/\delta}(-hd)|}. \end{aligned}$$

Notice that $\frac{n}{\delta} \geq 2$ since $\delta \mid n$ and $\delta < n$. Now Lemma 6 with $q = \frac{n}{\delta}$ and $\ell = d$ yields

$$\sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{(n, k)^{1/2}}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-k)|} \leq \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\delta|n} \delta^{-1/2} \log\left(\frac{en}{\delta}\right) \leq \frac{1}{2} n^{1/2} \sigma_{1/2}(n) \log(en).$$

□

4.2. Finalizing the Proof of Theorem 3

The orthogonality relations for additive characters yield

$$\begin{aligned} S_2(n, m) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ (b,n)=1}}^n b \sum_{k=1}^n e_n(k(m\bar{a} - b)) \\ &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ (b,n)=1}}^n b e_n(-kb). \end{aligned}$$

We start by isolating the term corresponding to $k = n$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} S_2(n, m) &= \frac{1}{4} n (\varphi(n))^2 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ (b,n)=1}}^n b e_n(-kb) \\ &:= \frac{1}{4} n (\varphi(n))^2 + R_2(n, m). \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Applying Lemma 4, we first derive

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_2(n, m) &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \left(-n \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}} \frac{\mu(d)}{1 - e_{n/d}(-k)} + \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d < n \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1 \right) \right) \\
 &= - \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{1 - e_{n/d}(-k)} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d < n}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1 \right) \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} | k}}^{n-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \\
 &:= R_{21}(n, m) + R_{22}(n, m).
 \end{aligned}$$

Lemmas 2 and 7 yield

$$\begin{aligned}
 |R_{21}(n, m)| &\leq \sum_{d|n} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-k)|} \left| \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_n(km\bar{a}) \right| \\
 &\leq 2n^{3/2} \tau(n) \log(en) \sum_{d|n} \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ \frac{n}{d} \nmid k}}^{n-1} \frac{(n, k)^{1/2}}{|1 - e_{n/d}(-k)|} \\
 &\leq n^2 \sigma_{1/2}(n) \tau(n) (\log en)^2 \sum_{d|n} 1 \\
 &= n^2 \sigma_{1/2}(n) (\tau(n) \log en)^2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Now setting $k = \frac{hn}{d}$ in the sum over k in $R_{22}(n, m)$ yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{22}(n, m) &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d < n}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1 \right) \sum_{h=1}^{d-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(hm\bar{a}) \\
 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ 1 < d < n}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1 \right) \sum_{h=1}^{d-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(hm\bar{a}).
 \end{aligned}$$

It should be pointed out that $d \mid n$ and $d > 1$ imply that $d \nmid \bar{a}$. Now inverting the summations, we derive, for all $d \mid n$ such that $1 < d < n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=1}^{d-1} \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(hm\bar{a}) &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a \sum_{h=1}^{d-1} e_d(hm\bar{a}) = \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(m\bar{a}) \times \frac{1 - e_d((d-1)m\bar{a})}{1 - e_d(m\bar{a})} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(m\bar{a}) \times \frac{1 - e_d(-m\bar{a})}{1 - e_d(m\bar{a})} \\ &= - \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a e_d(m\bar{a}) e_d(-m\bar{a}) \\ &= - \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,n)=1}}^n a = -\frac{n\varphi(n)}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

so that, since $n \geq 2$,

$$R_{22}(n, m) = -\frac{n\varphi(n)}{4} \sum_{\substack{d \mid n \\ 1 < d < n}} \mu(d) \left(\frac{n}{d} - 1\right) = \frac{n^2\varphi(n)}{4} - \frac{n\varphi(n)^2}{4} - \frac{n\varphi(n)}{4}, \quad (9)$$

where we used the well-known Dirichlet convolution identities $\sum_{d \mid n} \mu(d) = 0$ if $n > 1$ and $\sum_{d \mid n} \frac{\mu(d)}{d} = \frac{\varphi(n)}{n}$. The result follows by inserting the estimates (8) and (9) in Equation (7). \square

5. Proof of Theorem 4

Let $n \geq 3$ be odd. Using orthogonality relations for Dirichlet characters, we get by the proof of Theorem 1

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,n)=1}}^n |S_2(n, m) - 4^{-1}n^2\varphi(n)|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)^2} \sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,n)=1}}^n \left| \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} \bar{\chi}(m) \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right) \right|^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)^2} \sum_{\substack{\chi_1 \pmod{n} \\ \chi_1 \neq \chi_0}} \sum_{\substack{\chi_2 \pmod{n} \\ \chi_2 \neq \chi_0}} \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a\chi_1(a) \right)^2 \left(\sum_{a=1}^n a\bar{\chi}_2(a) \right)^2 \underbrace{\sum_{\substack{m=1 \\ (m,n)=1}}^n \chi_1(m)\bar{\chi}_2(m)}_{= \varphi(n) \text{ if } \chi_1 = \chi_2, 0 \text{ if not}} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi \neq \chi_0}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4 = \frac{1}{\varphi(n)} \sum_{\substack{\chi \pmod{n} \\ \chi(-1)=-1}} \left| \sum_{a=1}^n a\chi(a) \right|^4$$

by the remark (6), and the proof follows by using Lemma 1 with $q = n$ and $\ell = 0$. \square

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